

High-Risk Without Safeguards? The EU AI Act and the Deregulation of Medical AI

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly embedded in clinical decision-making, yet recent reforms to the European Union (EU) Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act) risk creating a category of high-risk medical AI systems without corresponding safeguards. In the current framework, AI-enabled medical devices are regulated through a combination of sectoral medical device legislation, the Medical Devices Regulation (MDR) and In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices Regulation (IVDR), and additional AI-specific safeguards in the AI Act. Recent EU “simplification” initiatives, including the Digital Omnibus and the Health Innovation Package, propose to remove these safeguards. This narrative review analyses recent EU legislative developments and their impact on the relationship between the AI Act and medical device law. It shows that the proposed reforms would retain the high-risk classification of AI-enabled medical devices while removing most associated AI Act obligations. In effect, this decouples risk classification from the safeguards that give it regulatory meaning, including requirements on data governance, risk management, human oversight, and post-market monitoring. Rather than resolving regulatory overlap, the reforms shift the centre of gravity back to product-focused medical device law without ensuring equivalent AI-specific safeguards. These changes may narrow attention to fundamental rights, weaken oversight in clinical use, and increase legal uncertainty regarding accountability and responsibility. In a domain where AI systems directly shape clinical decisions and patient outcomes, these changes risk undermining the conditions for safe, equitable, and accountable deployment of medical AI.

1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) is rapidly becoming embedded in clinical decision-making, from radiology to emergency care. While these technologies promise improvements in diagnostic accuracy and efficiency, they also introduce risks that arise across the AI lifecycle, from data collection and model design to deployment and real-world clinical use.^{1,2} Recognising these challenges, the European Union (EU) adopted the Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act),³ which

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¹ Van Kolfschooten H. The AI Cycle of Health Inequity and Digital Ageism: Mitigating Biases through the EU Regulatory Framework on Medical Devices. *Journal of Law and the Biosciences* 2023;10:lsad031. doi.org/10.1093/jlb/lsad031.

² Leslie D, Mazumder A, Peppin A, Wolters MK et al. Does “AI” Stand for Augmenting Inequality in the Era of Covid-19 Healthcare? *BMJ* 2021;372:n304. doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n304.

³ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act) (Text with EEA relevance) PE/24/2024/REV/1 OJ L, 2024/1689, 12.7.2024.

complements existing medical device legislation – the Medical Devices Regulation (MDR)⁴ and In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices Regulation (IVDR).⁵ It introduces additional safeguards tailored to AI-specific risks, including requirements relating to data governance, transparency, human oversight, and post-market monitoring.⁶ However, this ‘horizontal’, cross-sectoral approach to AI regulation is now increasingly contested.^{7,8}

Under the EU’s broader “simplification” agenda,⁹ recent proposals such as the Digital Omnibus¹⁰ and the Health Innovation Package^{11,12,13} aim to substantially narrow legal safeguards for medical AI. First, the European Commission proposed in its Health Innovation Package to move AI-enabled medical devices regulated under the MDR and IVDR from Annex I, Section A to Section B of the AI Act. Second, in its response to the European Commission’s Digital Omnibus Proposal, the European Parliament proposed to delete Section A altogether, incorporating its legislation into Section B, and amending Article 2(2) so that Annex I systems would be subject only to a limited subset of AI Act safeguards. In these scenarios, while these systems would remain formally classified as “high-risk,” they would no longer be subject to the safeguards that give that classification regulatory meaning, effectively decoupling legal classification from legal consequence.¹⁴ Our concern is not the pursuit of regulatory simplification *per se*. Instead, we argue that simplification is being pursued at the wrong regulatory layer. It would be more prudent to simplify existing procedures and administrative processes whilst preserving important safeguards that already exist for high-risk AI systems.

This article reviews recent EU regulatory developments concerning AI in medical devices and examines their implications for the governance of medical AI in healthcare. Drawing on EU legislation, policy proposals, regulatory guidance, and academic literature, it shows that, although

⁴ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC (Text with EEA relevance). OJ L 117, 5.5.2017, pp. 1–175.

⁵ Regulation (EU) 2017/746 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices and repealing Directive 98/79/EC and Commission Decision 2010/227/EU (Text with EEA relevance) OJ L 117, 5.5.2017, pp. 176–332.

⁶ Chapter III, Regulation (EU) 2024/1689.

⁷ Open Letter: No fragmentation of EU AI Act – Preserve the horizontal approach [online]. 11 March 2026. https://allai.nl/wp-content/uploads/2026/03/Open-Letter_AI-Omnibus_AI-Act_ANNEX-IA-to-IB.pdf (accessed 7 April 2026).

⁸ Van Kolfshoeten H, Solaiman B, Onitiu D. Medical AI at Risk: Digital Omnibus Amendments Undermine Safeguards in Healthcare [online]. 24 March 2026. <https://haiweb.org/storage/2026/03/Medical-AI-at-Risk.pdf> (accessed 7 April 2026).

⁹ A simpler and faster Europe: Communication on implementation and simplification (European Commission 2024-2029) https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/8556fc33-48a3-4a96-94e8-8ecacef1ea18_en?filename=250201_Simplification_Communication_en.pdf.

¹⁰ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulations (EU) 2024/1689 and (EU) 2018/1139 as regards the simplification of the implementation of harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Digital Omnibus on AI) (Text with EEA relevance) {SWD(2025) 836 final} COM(2025) 836 final, 2025/0359(COD).

¹¹ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulations (EU) 2017/745 and (EU) 2017/746 as regards simplifying and reducing the burden of the rules on medical devices and in vitro diagnostic medical devices, and amending Regulation (EU) 2022/123 as regards the support of the European Medicines Agency for the expert panels on medical devices and Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 as regards the list of Union harmonisation legislation referred to in its Annex I {SWD(2025) 1050-1052 final} (Text with EEA relevance) 16.12.2025, COM(2025) 1023 final 2025/0404 (COD).

¹² European Commission. New measures to make EU health sector more innovative, competitive and resilient [online]. 16 December 2025. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_25_3077

¹³ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulations (EU) 2017/745 and (EU) 2017/746 as regards simplifying and reducing the burden of the rules on medical devices and in vitro diagnostic medical devices, and amending Regulation (EU) 2022/123 as regards the support of the European Medicines Agency for the expert panels on medical devices and Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 as regards the list of Union harmonisation legislation referred to in its Annex I {SWD(2025) 1050-1052 final} (Text with EEA relevance) 16.12.2025, COM(2025) 1023 final 2025/0404 (COD).

¹⁴ European Parliament. Artificial Intelligence Act: delayed application, ban on nudifier apps. [online] 26 March 2026. <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20260323IPR38829/artificial-intelligence-act-delayed-application-ban-on-nudifier-apps> (accessed 8 April 2026).

presented as simplification, the proposed reforms risk hollowing out the AI Act's high-risk framework for medical AI without ensuring that equivalent safeguards for safe, equitable, and responsible AI are maintained elsewhere. Given the EU's role as a global regulatory standard-setter, these developments raise broader legal, ethical, and social questions about how AI should be governed in healthcare, particularly in relation to patient safety, health equity, and accountability in clinical decision-making.

2. The AI Act's original design: AI-specific safeguards for medical devices

When the AI Act was adopted in 2024, the EU legislator classified AI systems that are safety components of medical devices regulated under the Medical Devices Regulation (MDR) or the In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices Regulation (IVDR) as high-risk AI systems (Annex I, Section A). In practice, this meant that manufacturers of AI-enabled medical devices had to undergo conformity assessment under the MDR or IVDR while also complying with additional safeguards introduced by the AI Act.¹⁵ These included requirements on data governance and dataset quality, risk management, transparency and technical documentation, human oversight, and post-market monitoring. The purpose of these rules was to address risks associated with AI systems that traditional medical device legislation was not designed to capture.^{16,17}

The need for these additional safeguards stems from the way AI-based systems differ from traditional medical devices, including conventional medical software. Traditional devices are typically rule-based and relatively stable: they are assessed in terms of whether they perform their intended function safely and reliably under (pre-)defined conditions. However, some AI systems may produce systematically different outcomes across patient groups or clinical settings when deployed on the ground.^{18,19,20}

These characteristics give rise to two distinct regulatory challenges. First, AI-based medical devices must be assessed not only for laboratory performance, but also for their real-world clinical performance across diverse populations and settings.^{21,22} Secondly, some AI systems continue to learn or adapt after deployment. While this may improve performance in some cases, it can also introduce new risks or degrade performance over time if changes are not effectively monitored.²³

¹⁵ Van Kolschooten H, Van Oirschot J. The EU Artificial Intelligence Act (2024): Implications for Healthcare. *Health Policy* 2024;149:105152. doi.org/10.1016/j.healthpol.2024

¹⁶ Van Kolschooten H. The AI Cycle of Health Inequity and Digital Ageism: Mitigating Biases through the EU Regulatory Framework on Medical Devices. *Journal of Law and the Biosciences* 2023;10:lsad031. doi.org/10.1093/jlb/lsad031.

¹⁷ Onituu D, Wachter S, Mittelstadt, B. How AI Challenges the Medical Device Regulation: Patient Safety, Benefits, and Intended Uses. *Journal of Law and the Biosciences* 2024:lsae007. doi.org/10.1093/jlb/lsae007.

¹⁸ Amin A., Acharya D, Koteswara P. et al. A systematic literature review on mammography: deep learning techniques for breast cancer detection with global and Asian perspectives. *BMC Cancer* 2025;25:1627. doi.org/10.1186/s12885-025-14876-5.

¹⁹ Oberije CJG, Currie R, Leaver A et al. Assessing artificial intelligence in breast screening with stratified results on 306 839 mammograms across geographic regions, age, breast density and ethnicity: A Retrospective Investigation Evaluating Screening (ARIES) study. *BMJ Health & Care Inform.* 2025;32:e101318. doi.org/10.1136/bmjhci-2024-101318.

²⁰ Daneshjou R, Vodrahalli K, Novoa R. et al. Disparities in dermatology AI performance on a diverse, curated clinical image set. *Sci. Adv.* 2022;8:eabq6147. doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abq6147.

²¹ Gerke S, Babic B, Evgeniou, T. The need for a system view to regulate artificial intelligence/machine learning-based software as medical device. *NPJ Digital Medicine* 2020;53:1-2.

²² Gichoya JW, Banerjee I, Bhimireddy AR et al. AI recognition of patient race in medical imaging: a modelling study. *The Lancet Digital Health* 2022;4:406-414. doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500(22)00063-2.

²³ Gerke S, Babic B, Evgeniou, T. The need for a system view to regulate artificial intelligence/machine learning-based software as medical device. *NPJ Digital Medicine* 2020;53:1-2.

These challenges are only partly addressed by the existing EU medical device framework, which is primarily oriented towards evaluating products at the point of market entry. By contrast, many risks associated with medical AI arise across the system's lifecycle, including development, deployment, and clinical use, and may reinforce existing inequalities.²⁴ These include not only technical forms of bias, such as unrepresentative training data, but also contextual risks arising from how systems are used in practice, including disparities in access, digital literacy, and clinical decision-making.²⁵ A simplification agenda should ideally contend with preserving meaningful safeguards across that entire lifecycle.²⁶

The AI Act was therefore designed to complement the MDR and IVDR by introducing governance requirements tailored to AI systems across their lifecycle. The introduction of these safeguards reflects the legislator's view that existing medical device law alone is insufficient to address the distinctive risks of medical AI. The Commission's reform proposal, however, rests on a different diagnosis: that the current framework creates unnecessary regulatory overlap.

3. Is regulatory overlap really the problem?

The Commission justifies the proposed reform primarily by the wish to lower administrative burdens, pointing to regulatory overlap between the AI Act and existing medical device legislation. There is some basis for these concerns. Since the entry into application of the MDR and IVDR, the regulatory framework for medical technologies has become more demanding than under the previous directives. Stricter clinical evidence requirements, limited capacity among notified bodies, and complex conformity assessment procedures have made it more complex to bring certain medical devices to market.^{27,28,29}

However, attributing these burdens to the AI Act risks misidentifying the source of the problem.³⁰ The AI Act was not designed to introduce a separate regulatory pathway for AI-enabled medical devices. Instead, it was intended to operate alongside existing sectoral legislation such as the MDR and IVDR. Recital 64 of the AI Act explicitly recognises that multiple EU legal frameworks may apply to the same product where they address different risks.³¹ This logic is reflected in the structure of the Regulation itself. Rather than establishing a parallel approval pathway, the AI Act integrates its requirements into the conformity assessment procedures already required under sectoral

²⁴ Gerke S. Health AI for good rather than evil? The need for a new regulatory framework for AI-based medical devices. *Yale J. Health Pol'y L. & Ethics*. 2021;20:432.

²⁵ Van Kolschooten H. The AI Cycle of Health Inequity and Digital Ageism: Mitigating Biases through the EU Regulatory Framework on Medical Devices. *Journal of Law and the Biosciences* 2023;10:lsad031. doi.org/10.1093/jlb/lsad031.

²⁶ Solaiman, B., Mekki, Y.M., Qadir, J. *et al.* A "True Lifecycle Approach" towards governing healthcare AI with the GCC as a global governance model. *npj Digit. Med.* 8, 337 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-025-01614-1>; Solaiman B. From Bench to Bedside: Governing Health Care Artificial Intelligence (AI) through a "True Lifecycle Approach." *American Journal of Law & Medicine*. 2025;51(3-4):452-478. doi:10.1017/amj.2025.10091.

²⁷ See also European Parliament resolution of 23 October 2024 on the urgent need to revise the Medical Devices Regulation (2024/2849 (RSP)) (29 January 2025) P10_TA (2024) 0028.

²⁸ Joint paper of Croatia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Luxembourg, Romania, Malta and Slovenia on necessary reforms in MDR and IVDR: priorities / main points (28 November 2024) 15380/24.

²⁹ European Parliamentary Research Service, Briefing EU Legislation in Progress: Medical devices: Simplifying the rules (PE 785.663, March 2026) [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIEF/2026/785663/EPRS_BRI\(2026\)785663_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIEF/2026/785663/EPRS_BRI(2026)785663_EN.pdf).

³⁰ A recent empirical study finds finding that stakeholders primarily identify regulatory fragmentation across overlapping EU instruments, rather than the AI Act itself, as the main source of compliance challenges: Hacker P, Kilian R and Costas J. "Simplifying" European AI Regulation: An Evidence-based White Paper. Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2025.

³¹ AI Act, recital 64, art 11(2), art 43(3).

legislation. Article 43(3) allows compliance with the AI Act to be assessed within the same procedures applicable under the MDR and IVDR, while Article 11(2) permits the use of a single set of technical documentation to demonstrate compliance with both frameworks. This design does not require two separate regulatory processes. Instead, testing, documentation, and assessment can be aligned within a single integrated procedure. This follows the AI Act's own architecture where it allows providers to integrate requirements on testing, reporting and documentation with sector-specific procedures.³² This reading is confirmed by a recent guidance document on the interplay between the MDR/IVDR and the AI Act, endorsed by the Artificial Intelligence Board and the Medical Device Coordination Group.³³

The next section examines how the proposed reforms would modify the relationship between the AI Act and medical device legislation.

4. The Commission's proposal: narrowing the obligations for AI medical devices

The Commission's proposal within the Health Innovation Package modifies the relationship between medical device legislation and the AI Act. Importantly, it does not change the scope of the AI Act or the classification of AI-enabled medical devices as high-risk systems. AI systems embedded in medical devices regulated under the MDR or IVDR would therefore remain formally included within Annex I – the high-risk category – of the AI Act.

However, the proposal introduces a significant structural change by moving AI-enabled medical devices from Section A to Section B of Annex I.³⁴ This is consequential because AI-based medical devices would retain the 'high-risk' label while most safeguards underpinning that label are removed. First, under Article 2(2), Section B systems are excluded from the high-risk regime under Chapter III (and remain subject to only a narrow subset of provisions).³⁵ In effect, the core requirements relating to risk management, data governance, human oversight, and post-market monitoring would, therefore, no longer apply. Second, the narrow subset of provisions that continue to apply are restricted to Article 6(1), Article 60a, Articles 102-109, Articles 111 and 112, with Article 57 applying only where the high-risk requirements have been integrated into the relevant sectoral legislation. These remaining provisions are largely procedural (for example, regulatory sandboxes and transitional provisions) and do not impose substantive requirements on developers or users. In practice, AI-enabled medical devices would retain the "high-risk" label while most safeguards attached to it would be removed.

³² Regulation (EU) 2024/1689, recital 64; arts 8(2), 11(2), 43(3). Artificial Intelligence Board; Medical Device Coordination Group. Interplay between the Medical Devices Regulation (MDR) & In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices Regulation (IVDR) and the Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA). AIB 2025-1/MDCG 2025-6. June 2025. pp. 2–3.

³³ Artificial Intelligence Board (AIB) and the Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG). Interplay between the Medical Devices Regulation (MDR) & In vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices Regulation (IVDR) and the Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA). [online] June 2025 https://health.ec.europa.eu/document/download/b78a17d7-e3cd-4943-851d-e02a2f22bbb4_en?filename=mdcg_2025-6_en.pdf.

³⁴ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulations (EU) 2017/745 and (EU) 2017/746 as regards simplifying and reducing the burden of the rules on medical devices and in vitro diagnostic medical devices, and amending Regulation (EU) 2022/123 as regards the support of the European Medicines Agency for the expert panels on medical devices and Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 as regards the list of Union harmonisation legislation referred to in its Annex I {SWD(2025) 1050-1052 final} (Text with EEA relevance) 16.12.2025, COM(2025) 1023 final 2025/0404 (COD).

³⁵ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689, art 2(2). European Parliament. Amendments adopted on 26 Mar 2026 on COM(2025)0836. Amendment 27 (Art 2(2)).

At the same time, parallel reform efforts under the Digital Omnibus initially suggested a different regulatory trajectory. The Commission’s proposal aimed to streamline compliance by integrating AI Act requirements into existing MDR and IVDR conformity assessments, allowing a single process to satisfy both frameworks.³⁶ This approach built on earlier guidance emphasising procedural alignment and the avoidance of duplication. However, the European Parliament has since adopted amendments within the Digital Omnibus framework that move in the same direction as the Health Innovation Package. In particular, it proposes to shift products covered by sectoral legislation, including medical devices, from Section A to Section B of Annex I. As a result, although the Commission’s approach was based on procedural integration, the emerging legislative position points towards a reduction of AI-specific safeguards. The combined effect is therefore not simplification through integration, but a substantive narrowing of safeguards for medical AI.

In addition, the proposal creates scope for the Commission to introduce AI-specific requirements through implementing acts, delegated acts, and common specifications under the MDR and IVDR, taking into account the AI Act’s Chapter III, Section 2 requirements.³⁷ Consequently, safeguards removed at this stage could be reintroduced through a different regulatory route. It also expands the role of regulatory sandboxes, including opportunities for real-world testing of AI systems and support for innovation, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises.³⁸ While these developments may indicate that AI governance is not being removed entirely, they also suggest a shift towards re-sectoralising aspects of AI regulation within medical device law, rather than maintaining a horizontal framework under the AI Act.

Figure 1. Original and proposed EU regulatory framework for AI-enabled medical devices

³⁶Article 1(2) of Digital Omnibus on AI proposal: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52025PC0836>.

³⁷ Article 57 (3a) amendment Digital Omnibus.

³⁸ This has been suggested in academic research before as an important regulatory feature for medical device regulation, see Li P, Williams R, Gilbert S. Regulating Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning-Enabled Medical Devices in Europe and the United Kingdom. *Law, Technology and Humans* 2023;5:94-101.

As shown in Figure 1, the proposed reform therefore alters the regulatory framework for medical AI in three important respects. First, the core obligations normally attached to the AI Act's high-risk classification would no longer apply, including requirements relating to data governance, risk management, transparency, human oversight, and post-market monitoring. Second, the scope of actors subject to regulatory duties would narrow. Under the current AI Act framework, certain obligations apply not only to manufacturers but also to deployers of AI systems, including healthcare institutions responsible for integrating such tools into clinical practice, for example through duties relating to training, monitoring, and record-keeping.³⁹ Under the Commission's proposal, these deployer obligations would no longer apply to medical AI systems. Third, the nature of risk governance would shift. While the MDR and IVDR require manufacturers to implement risk management systems focused on safety and performance, the AI Act requires providers to identify and mitigate risks posed by AI systems not only to health and safety but also to broader fundamental rights, including risks related to non-discrimination, privacy, and access to healthcare.⁴⁰ If adopted, the reform would remove this broader dimension from the regulation of AI medical devices. These changes have important implications for patient safety, health equity, and the overall coherence of the regulatory framework, which are examined in the following section.

³⁹ Article 26 AI Act.

⁴⁰ Recital 1 AI Act.

5. What is at stake: safety, equity, and regulatory coherence in healthcare

These developments have implications not only for regulatory design, but also for the ethical, legal, and social dimensions of AI use in healthcare. While the MDR/IVDR provide an extensive framework for assessing the safety and performance of medical devices, they were not designed to govern AI-specific issues such as algorithmic bias, human oversight in clinical use, or broader fundamental-rights risks. The following sections examine three consequences of the proposed reform: the narrowing of the AI Act's fundamental-rights perspective, the removal of deployer obligations governing clinical use, and the legal uncertainty and consequential barriers to AI adoption.

5.1 Narrowing the fundamental-rights dimension

The AI Act is distinctive in that it combines elements of product safety regulation with a focus on fundamental rights risks associated with AI systems.⁴¹ This is particularly important in the healthcare context, where AI systems directly affect legally protected interests such as the right to health, non-discrimination, privacy, and human dignity.^{42,43} While AI-enabled medical devices are not subject to the fundamental rights impact assessment (FRIA) under Article 27,⁴⁴ this does not mean that fundamental-rights considerations are absent. Rather, the AI Act embeds such concerns throughout the high-risk framework itself.⁴⁵ The obligations in Articles 8-15, covering data governance, risk management, transparency, human oversight, and post-market monitoring, are framed as protecting not only health and safety, but also fundamental rights. The proposed reform therefore does not merely remove an additional layer of rights-based assessment; it removes the core mechanisms through which these concerns are operationalised in the governance of medical AI.

This shift is particularly relevant because many of the key risks of medical AI, such as algorithmic bias and unequal clinical outcomes, are not only technical issues but raise fundamental rights concerns, including discrimination and unequal access to healthcare.⁴⁶ Under the full high-risk framework of the AI Act, developers would be required to implement a risk management system and ensure that training datasets are appropriate, representative, and free of biases (Articles 9-10). Hospitals deploying the system would also need to ensure that clinicians receive appropriate training and that the system's use is monitored (Article 26). If these requirements no longer apply, the system would still undergo MDR conformity assessment, but without explicit obligations to identify or mitigate such biases. Real-world testing and regulatory sandboxes may help identify such

⁴¹ Almada M, Petit N. The EU AI Act: Between the Rock of Product Safety and the Hard Place of Fundamental Rights. *Common Market Law Review* 2025:62.

⁴² Solaiman B. The European Union's Artificial Intelligence Act and 'Trust: Towards an AI Bill of Rights in Healthcare? *Law, Innovation and Technology* 2025:17;318. doi.org/10.1080/17579961.2025.2469986.

⁴³ Van Kolschooten H. Towards an EU Charter of Digital Patients' Rights in the Age of Artificial Intelligence. *Digital Society* 2025:4. doi.org/10.1007/s44206-025-00159-w.

⁴⁴ Mantelero A. The Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment (FRIA) in the AI Act: Roots, Legal Obligations and Key Elements for a Model Template. *Computer Law & Security Review* 2024:54;106020. doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2024.106020.

⁴⁵ Pham BC, Davies SR. What problems is the AI act solving? Technological solutionism, fundamental rights, and trustworthiness in European AI policy. *Critical Policy Studies* 2025:19;318-336. doi.org/10.1080/19460171.2024.2373786.

⁴⁶ Haider SA, Borna S, Gomez-Cabello CA. et al. The Algorithmic Divide: A Systematic Review on AI-Driven Racial Disparities in Healthcare. *J. Racial and Ethnic Health Disparities* 2026:13;188-217. doi.org/10.1007/s40615-024-02237-0

risks, but they are selective, time-limited, and no substitute for system-wide obligations on data governance, human oversight, accuracy, and post-market monitoring.^{47,48}

One concern relates to the quality and representativeness of training data. Machine-learning systems depend on their training data, and if these do not reflect diverse patient populations, outputs may produce systematic disparities in diagnostic accuracy or risk prediction.⁴⁹ For example, an AI system designed to predict cardiovascular risk may perform differently across demographic groups if its training data disproportionately represent certain populations.⁵⁰ Empirical research shows that systems performing well in controlled settings may behave differently in clinical workflows, particularly when deployed in hospitals with different patient populations or data infrastructures.⁵¹

While the MDR and IVDR may address some forms of *technical* bias through safety and performance assessment, they do not capture *contextual* biases arising in the deployment and use of AI systems, such as unequal access, differential treatment of patients, or disparities linked to digital literacy and healthcare infrastructure.⁵² The AI Act partially addresses this by regulating both providers and deployers of high-risk AI systems – a feature that becomes particularly significant in light of the proposed removal of deployer obligations, discussed below.⁵³

5.2 No more deployer obligations: weakened human oversight in clinical practice

Under the current AI Act framework, deployers of high-risk AI systems are subject to obligations concerning use of AI systems in accordance with instructions, human oversight, quality control of input data, monitoring, log retention, and incident reporting. It should be noted that the ‘deployer’ under the AI Act is not the same as the ‘user’ under the MDR/IVDR. Under the joint AIB/MDCG guidance, the concept of a ‘deployer’ under the AI Act cannot be equated with the MDR/IVDR understanding of a healthcare professional or lay user. In practice, the ‘deployer’ will often be the healthcare institution that uses the AI system in its organisational workflow.⁵⁴ In the absence of EU-level deployer obligations under the AI Act, responsibility for these aspects of AI use is therefore left to national law and professional standards within Member States. This risks uneven oversight across Member States and variation in how healthcare institutions manage AI-related risks. The proposed disapplication of deployer obligations will, therefore, create a regulatory blind spot at the point of use.

⁴⁷ Arts. 59b (2) and 59c (1) of the simplification proposal.

⁴⁸ AI Act, art 57 and art 60; Proposal for a Regulation ... COM(2025) 1023 final, proposed MDR/IVDR sandbox provisions; Proposal for a Regulation ... COM(2025) 836 final, proposed art 60a.

⁴⁹ Celi LA, Cellini J, Charpignon ML et al. Sources of bias in artificial intelligence that perpetuate healthcare disparities—A global review. PLOS Digital Health 2022. doi.org/10.1371/journal.pdig.0000022.

⁵⁰ Cau R, Pisu F, Suri JS et al. Addressing hidden risks: Systematic review of artificial intelligence biases across racial and ethnic groups in cardiovascular diseases. European Journal of Radiology 2025;183:111867. doi.org/10.1016/j.ejrad.2024.111867.

⁵¹ Longhurst CA et al. A Call for Artificial Intelligence Implementation Science Centers to Evaluate Clinical Effectiveness. NEJM AI 2024;1(8). doi.org/10.1056/AIp2400223.

⁵² Leslie D, Mazumder A, Peppin A, Wolters MK et al. Does “AI” Stand for Augmenting Inequality in the Era of Covid-19 Healthcare? BMJ 2021;372:n304. doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n304.

⁵³ Van Kolschooten H. The AI Cycle of Health Inequity and Digital Ageism: Mitigating Biases through the EU Regulatory Framework on Medical Devices. Journal of Law and the Biosciences 2023;10:lsad031. doi.org/10.1093/jlb/lsad031.

⁵⁴ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689, art 26; Artificial Intelligence Board; Medical Device Coordination Group. Interplay between the MDR/IVDR and the AIA. AIB 2025-1/MDCG 2025-6. June 2025. p. 2.

From a patient safety perspective, this is problematic because AI safety depends not only on technical performance, but on how systems are used in practice.⁵⁵ AI tools in healthcare are typically introduced as decision-support systems, meaning that their outputs must be interpreted, contextualised, and, where necessary, challenged by clinicians.⁵⁶ Meaningful oversight requires organisational measures such as training, performance monitoring, and mechanisms to detect and respond to errors.⁵⁷ Recent research on clinical workflows underscores that safe implementation requires technological robustness, humans in the loop, and ethical safeguards operating together, rather than a narrow focus on model performance only.⁵⁸ Without deployer obligations ensuring these conditions, there is a risk that AI systems are used in ways that compromise patient safety, for example through over-reliance on automated outputs or failure to detect system errors in practice.

The removal of deployer obligations further weakens the ability to identify and address biases that arise in clinical use. As discussed above, many biases in medical AI arise in the context of deployment rather than solely in system design. These risks cannot be addressed through product regulation alone.⁵⁹ Although healthcare professionals must report serious incidents under the MDR/IVDR, these obligations are largely reactive and limited to safety events. Gradual harms, such as biased performance across patient groups, may remain invisible without obligations to log AI use and monitor outcomes.

5.3 Legal uncertainty, fragmentation, and legal barriers to AI adoption

Legal uncertainty is already a major barrier to the adoption of artificial intelligence in healthcare. According to a WHO/Europe report on AI readiness, 86% of responding states identify legal uncertainty as a key constraint, while only a small minority have developed health-specific liability frameworks. At the same time, clear rules on accountability and liability for manufacturers, deployers, and users are seen as essential enablers of safe and effective AI use.^{60,61} A reform presented as simplification for innovation may reduce certain compliance burdens, but it may also shift and deepen uncertainty about accountability, responsibility, and the safe uptake of AI systems in practice.⁶²

Against this background, the proposed reform does not resolve existing uncertainty, but introduces a form of legal ambiguity that can be described as ‘signalling incoherence’. In risk-based regulation, classification systems are intended to perform a core function of prioritisation, calibration, and

⁵⁵Li MM, Reis BY, Rodman A. et al. Scaling medical AI across clinical contexts. *Nat Med* 2026;32:439-448. doi.org/10.1038/s41591-025-04184-7.

⁵⁶ Abd-Alrazaq A, Solaiman B, Mekki YM, et al. Hype vs Reality in the Integration of Artificial Intelligence in Clinical Workflows. *JMIR Form Res.* 2025;9:e70921. doi.org/10.2196/70921.

⁵⁷ Busuioc M, AI algorithmic oversight: new frontiers in regulation. In: Maggetti M, Di Mascio F, Natalini A. eds. *Handbook of Regulatory Authorities*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing 2022:470-486.

⁵⁸ Abd-Alrazaq A, Solaiman B, Mekki YM, Al-Thani D, Farooq F, Alkubeyyer M, et al. Hype vs Reality in the Integration of Artificial Intelligence in Clinical Workflows. *JMIR Form Res.* 2025;9:e70921. pp. 1–2.

⁵⁹ Fraser A, Butchart E, Szymánsky et al. The Need for Transparency of Clinical Evidence for Medical Devices in Europe. *The Lancet* 2018;392:521. doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)31270-4.

⁶⁰ World Health Organization, Regional Office for Europe, Artificial intelligence is reshaping health systems: state of readiness across the WHO European Region (WHO, 19 November 2025) 24.

⁶¹ Morley J, Hine E, Roberts H et al. Global health in the age of AI: charting a course for ethical implementation and societal benefit. *Minds Mach.* 2025;35:31.

⁶² Coiera E. The Last Mile: Where Artificial Intelligence Meets Reality. *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 2019;21:e16323.

signalling, aligning regulatory obligations with the level of risk.⁶³ Under the EU AI Act, the designation of an AI system as “high-risk” is intended to trigger stringent obligations. Under the proposed reform, however, AI-enabled medical devices remain classified as high-risk while being exempted from most associated requirements, thereby misaligning the regulatory label and its legal consequences. This weakens the signalling function of risk classification.⁶⁴ When a high-risk label is no longer coupled with corresponding safeguards, it becomes unclear what compliance requires in practice. Rather than enhancing predictability, the reform creates a category that signals heightened concern without specifying its implications, undermining the coherence and trustworthiness of the AI Act’s risk-based framework.⁶⁵

More broadly, the reform contributes to a fragmented and unstable regulatory landscape. If AI-specific safeguards are removed from the horizontal framework and reintroduced through sectoral legislation such as the MDR/IVDR, developers may face diverging standards, timelines, and conformity assessment procedures across sectors. Instead of a single EU framework for high-risk AI, this would result in multiple overlapping regimes. Similar inconsistencies are already visible in the regulation of consumer-facing technologies and general-purpose AI, where systems that influence health-related decisions may fall outside medical device regulation depending on their intended purpose, despite their real-world impact on patient care.⁶⁶ Such misalignments increase compliance complexity and reduce legal certainty.

For patients, these forms of legal uncertainty translate into concrete risks. They may not be aware of when AI is used in diagnosis or treatment, how it influences clinical decision-making, or what safeguards apply. Where harm occurs, it may be difficult to determine who is responsible – clinicians, healthcare providers, or developers – particularly in the absence of clear and consistent obligations across the system.⁶⁷ Legal uncertainty may also undermine informed consent and obscure patterns of unequal outcomes, especially where AI systems perform differently across population groups. In this sense, fragmentation and signalling incoherence do not merely affect regulatory design, but directly shape the level of protection available to patients in practice.⁶⁸

Finally, the implications for innovation and competitiveness are more complex than the simplification narrative suggests. While the Commission presents the reform as reducing administrative burdens and increasing predictability, removing core AI-specific safeguards risks producing a less coherent regulatory regime. In the longer term, this may undermine rather than strengthen the EU’s ambition to provide a ‘simple’ and trusted environment guiding the development of medical AI.⁶⁹

⁶³ Baldwin, R. and Black, J. Really Responsive Regulation. *The Modern Law Review* 2008;71;59-94. doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2230.2008.00681.x

⁶⁴ Rothstein H, Huber M, Gaskell G. A theory of risk colonization: The spiralling regulatory logics of societal and institutional risk. *Economy and Society* 2006;35(1);91–112. doi.org/10.1080/03085140500465865.

⁶⁵ Veale M. A Critical Take on the Policy Recommendations of the EU High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence. *European Journal of Risk Regulation* 2020;11(1):e1. doi.org/10.1017/err.2019.65

⁶⁶ Van Kolfshoeten HB, Petročnik T. Emerging Shadow Health Systems: Regulating Health-Focused Generative AI Chatbots from a European perspective. *Zenodo* 2026. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19094764.

⁶⁷ Duffour MN, Gerke S. The proposed EU Directives for AI liability leave worrying gaps likely to impact medical AI. *npj Digit. Med.* 2023;6;77. doi.org/10.1038/s41746-023-00823-w.

⁶⁸ Del Rey Puech P, Saund J, Panteli D, McKee M. Demystifying artificial intelligence in health: what health policy-makers need to know. Copenhagen: European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies, WHO Regional Office for Europe; 2026. p. 177-187.

⁶⁹ Open Letter: No fragmentation of EU AI Act – Preserve the horizontal approach [online]. 11 March 2026. https://allai.nl/wp-content/uploads/2026/03/Open-Letter_AI-Omnibus_AI-Act_ANNEX-IA-to-IB.pdf (accessed 7 April 2026).

6. The legislative path ahead

The Commission's proposal must be understood within the EU's broader agenda of competitiveness and regulatory simplification. Reducing unnecessary administrative burdens and improving access to innovative medical technologies are legitimate policy goals, particularly in a sector characterised by high development costs and complex conformity assessment procedures. Indeed, a shift toward greater sectorisation in certain aspects of AI governance for medical devices could have long-term merits in streamlining cross-institutional coordination, provided that risks such as diverging standards, cross-sector fragmentation, and capacity gaps are addressed from the outset. Nevertheless, healthcare occupies a special place in the regulatory landscape. Medical technologies directly affect bodily integrity, patient safety, and access to care, often in situations of vulnerability and reliance on professional expertise. In this context, regulatory simplification must be balanced against the need to maintain safeguards addressing the distinctive risks of AI. In other words, simplification should not occur at the expense of lowering existing safeguards, nor should it postpone important questions about formulating AI-specific standards in a way that further undermines legal certainty.

The proposal will now be discussed in trilogue negotiations between the European Parliament, European Commission, and Council of the EU. The key legislative question is not whether simplification is desirable, but where it should occur. Many of the burdens identified by the Commission stem from the operation of the MDR and IVDR themselves. These challenges point towards a different, more principled route to simplification: reducing procedural and administrative complexity rather than weakening the substantive safeguards governing high-risk AI. This could include improving the capacity of notified bodies, aligning documentation requirements across regulatory frameworks, digitalising submission and reporting processes, developing integrated guidance for compliance, and strengthening coordination between oversight bodies. Such measures would simplify the compliance architecture while preserving the normative foundations of AI governance in healthcare. By contrast, removing AI-specific safeguards risks addressing the symptoms of regulatory complexity while exacerbating underlying uncertainty about accountability, responsibility, and safe use in practice.

Several regulatory pathways therefore remain open to legislators. One option would be to reject the proposed shift of AI-enabled medical devices from Section A to Section B of Annex I of the AI Act, thereby preserving the full set of high-risk obligations. A further possibility would be to classify certain categories of AI-enabled medical devices under Annex III of the AI Act through implementing acts, subjecting them to the high-risk regime of the AI Act without the sectoral link with the MDR/IVDR.⁷⁰ Alternatively, if legislators do decide to abandon the horizontal approach of the AI Act, equivalent AI-specific safeguards should be incorporated directly into the MDR and IVDR without further delay and to set an appropriate baseline. It is, however, questionable whether safeguards relating to fundamental rights and deployer duties will be incorporated into this manufacturer-focused product safety framework.

⁷⁰ Laux J, Wachter S, Mittelstadt, B. Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence and the European Union AI Act: On the Conflation of Trustworthiness and Acceptability of Risk. *Regulation & Governance* 2024;18. doi.org/10.1111/rego.12512.

The key issue is whether a high-risk label without meaningful AI-specific safeguards is sufficient in a sector as sensitive as healthcare. As AI becomes increasingly embedded in clinical decision-making, the challenge for EU policymakers is to ensure that regulatory simplification does not come at the expense of patient safety, health equity, and trust in healthcare systems. A high-risk label that no longer carries high-risk duties is not a simplified version of the original regulation. It is a different regulation altogether.

Acknowledgments: None.

Competing Interests: Authors declare no competing interests.

Funding: DO was supported by the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation in the framework of the Alexander von Humboldt Professorship (Humboldt Professor of Technology and Regulation) endowed by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research via the Hasso-Plattner-Institute. HvK and BS received no specific grant for this research from any funding agency in the public, commercial or not-for-profit sectors.